

Strategies for therapeutic hypometabothermia

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Abstract

Although therapeutic hypothermia and metabolic suppression have shown robust neuroprotection in experimental brain ischemia, systemic complications have limited their use in treating acute stroke patients. The core temperature and basic metabolic rate are tightly regulated and maintained in a very stable level in mammals. Simply lowering body temperature or metabolic rate is actually a brutal therapy that may cause more systemic as well as regional problems other than providing protection. These problems are commonly seen in hypothermia and barbiturate coma. The main innovative concept of this review is to propose thermogenically optimal and synergistic reduction of core temperature and metabolic rate in therapeutic hypometabothermia using novel and clinically practical approaches. When metabolism and body temperature are reduced in a systematically synergistic manner, the outcome will be maximal protection and safe recovery, which happen in natural process, such as in hibernation, daily torpor and estivation.

Key words: Hypothermia; metabolic suppression; cold adaption; thermoregulation; neuroprotection

Definition: Hypometabothermia: hypometabolism and hypothermia

1. Introduction

Neuroprotective means for ischemic stroke is desperately needed in clinical settings because thrombolytic treatment can only be delivered to a very limited fraction of stroke patients. Therapeutic metabolic suppression and hypothermia are troubled with severe complications. While investigators are desperately in searching for an effective and safe neuroprotective means for critical illness, nature has already provided a solution for these problems millions years ago. In hibernators body temperature can reach -1.97°C , metabolic rate can be reduced to 1.22% of euthermic base levels, (Buck and Barnes 2000; Karpovich *et al* 2009)^{1,2} (Buck and Barnes 2000; Karpovich *et al.* 2009) (Buck and Barnes 2000; Karpovich *et al.* 2009) and cerebral blood flow can drop below ischemic threshold, (Frerichs *et al* 1994) which are followed by complete recovery. The efficacy and safety in therapeutic hypometabothermia can be greatly improved by utilizing the strategies that hibernators use for surviving extreme living conditions. This is supported by: 1) hibernation is associated with differential expression of conserved genes, rather than novel hibernation specific genes, (Zhao *et al* 2010) human shares similar genome with hibernating mammals; (Andrews 2007) 2) human have the capability for enduring extremely low temperature; successful recovery from accidental hypothermia with body temperature reaching 16°C has been reported, (Wollenek *et al* 2002) 3) human can also enter into some kind of "pseudo-hibernation" status; *loska*, "winter sleep", was reported to be a common practice among ancient Russian peasants in the Pskov Government, where Russian peasants were alleged

to spend half year in sleep for dealing with famine; (BMJ1900 2000) practicing meditation can lower metabolic rate and enter a "pseudo-hibernation" status; Indian yogis being studied under laboratory conditions demonstrated their ability to drastically reduce metabolic rate and survive air-tight confinement for up to 8 days without injury. (Young and Taylor 1998) Although it is not possible to directly put human into hibernation, but what we have learnt from hibernation can make a difference in treating ischemic strokes.

2. Current problems and barriers in therapeutic hypometabothermia

2.1. Therapeutic hypothermia provides robust protection but it is troubled by thermoregulatory defenses.

Hypothermia therapy for patients is almost always counteracted by thermoregulatory defenses, (Sessler 2001) which include both visible (such as shivering and vasoconstriction) and invisible (metabolic rate increase in non-muscular organs) thermogenic responses. A decrease of 1.3°C of body temperature provokes a 3-fold increase in circulating catecholamine concentrations (Frank *et al* 1997). These thermoregulatory defenses need to be blunted for efficiently lowering body temperature and for avoiding complications. (Frank *et al* 1997; Greif *et al* 2003) Visible thermoregulatory defenses can be attenuated through drug-induced tolerance to cold. There is no single drug can induce therapeutic hypothermia to 33 to 34°C in human. A combination of meperidine and buspirone can reduce shivering threshold by 2.3°C . (Mokhtarani *et al* 2001) This

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temperature is far from the much lower body temperatures observed in hibernators, (Buck and Barnes 2000; Heldmaier *et al* 2004) although some optimization can be achieved through isolated core cooling, surface warming, (Kimberger *et al* 2007) or combined use of meperidine and buspirone.

2.2. Severe adverse effects of therapeutic hypothermia.

Moderate hypothermia (28–32°C) and deep hypothermia (<28 °C) are associated with more complications. (Matthew *et al* 2002) Major problems with therapeutic hypothermia include cardiac arrhythmia, hemodynamic instability, bleeding, electrolyte shift (such as hypokalemia), shivering, and pneumonia. A comparative analysis of comatose survivors after cardiac arrest shows increased rate of arrhythmia, pneumonia, sepsis, and electrolyte disorder in therapeutic hypothermia (74%) group than in standard treatment group (71%). Of these increased adverse effects, electrolyte disorder only happens in therapeutic hypothermia. (Holzer 2010; Merchant *et al* 2006; Sagalyn *et al* 2009) Severe hypokalemia, hypophosphatemia and hypomagnesemia happen during the cooling phase (Mirzoyev *et al* 2010; Polderman *et al* 2001) and hypokalemia is significantly associated with the development of polymorphic ventricular tachycardia. (Mirzoyev *et al* 2010) Hypothermia-induced hypokalemia is probably caused by a shift of potassium from the extracellular to intracellular or extra vascular spaces. Potassium therapy is associated with hyperkalemia during rewarming phase. (Koht *et al* 1983; Sprung *et al* 1991) These hypothermia-induced electrolyte shift and arrhythmia are attributable to increased blood catecholamine levels associated with hypothermia. (Frank *et al* 1995; Wood *et al* 1980) This is further supported by the evidence that adrenaline administration results in hypomagnesemia, hypokalemia, hypocalcemia and hyponatremia, which can be prevented by pretreatment of carvedilol, (Nahar and Akhter 2009) a non-selective beta blocker and alpha-1 blocker. Local use of epinephrine also causes hypokalemia and ECG changes. (Hahn and Lofgren 2000; Kubota *et al* 1993)

2.3. Severe complications of pharmacological suppression of metabolic rate.

Although metabolic suppression (Koerner and Brambrink 2006) has shown robust neuroprotection in experimental brain ischemia, drug-related systemic complications (Coupey 1997) have limited their use in treating acute stroke patients. Therapeutic barbiturate coma is troubled with complications, in which hepatic dysfunction, hypokalemia, respiratory complications and hypotension occur in 87%, 82%, 76%, and 58% patients, respectively. (Schalen *et al* 1992) Severe

life-threatening hypokalemia refractory to potassium therapy and rebound hyperkalemia have also been reported associated with barbiturate coma therapy. (Cairns *et al* 2002; Jung *et al* 2009; Neil and Dale 2009) Other anesthetics also have been reported to cause hypokalemia, such as lignocaine, (van Heerden and Chew 1996) and pentobarbital (Robson *et al* 1981). Many anesthetics, including isoflurane, sevoflurane, ketamine-medetomidine-atropine, ketamine/xylazine, avertine, have been reported to induce hyperglycemia. (Brown *et al* 2005; Saha *et al* 2005; Zuurbier *et al* 2008) The hyperglycemic response in ketamine- or pentobarbital-anesthetized rats can be abolished by adrenergic blockade. (Reyes Toso *et al* 1995)

3. Strategies for therapeutic hypometabothermia

3.1. Blocking cold/nociceptive cold signals

Hibernators in natural environment have already acclimated to cold weather before they undergo hibernation or torpor. Therefore, cold tolerance may play a role in reducing cold stress and thermoregulatory responses during hibernation and therapeutic hypothermia. Cold signal generation, transduction and processing are the first step for initiation of thermoregulatory responses. Even when cold perception is blocked or attenuated such as in comatose or anesthetic conditions, subconscious cold signal generation and processing are still functioning and leading to thermodefenses. Blunting or eliminating cold and nociceptive signals will theoretically reduce stress and thermoregulatory responses during therapeutic hypothermia for acute ischemic stroke.

3.1.1. Cold sensing receptors.

Cold signal is generated through transient receptor potential (TRP) channels A1 and M8. (McKemy 2005) TRPA1 is co-expressed in some neurons with the heat-gated channel TRPV1 (Kobayashi *et al* 2005; Story *et al* 2003) and is also activated by the pungent ingredients in mustard and cinnamon. TRPA1 mediates perception of noxious cold temperatures below 15°C, (Kwan and Corey 2009; Story *et al* 2003) and its activation merges both noxious cold and noxious heat due to the co-expression of TRPV1. (Story *et al* 2003) Non-painful cool temperatures in the range of 30–15°C is mediated through TRPM8 channel, (McKemy *et al* 2002; Peier *et al* 2002) which also mediates noxious cold perception. TRPA1-deficient mice show reduced sensitivity to cold nociception and noxious cold induced behavioral response. (Karashima *et al* 2009; Kwan *et al* 2006) TRPM8-deficient mice show strikingly reduced avoidance of cold temperatures, lack behavioral response to unpleasant cold stimulus, but have normal nociceptive-like responses to subzero centigrade temperatures. (Dhaka *et al* 2007) The

transduction of cold signals could be different between somatic and visceral sensory neurons and TRPA1 may be the major mediator of cold-evoked responses in vagal visceral neurons. (Fajardo et al 2008) TRPA1 can be inhibited by ruthenium red, (Brignell et al 2008) camphor, HC03001[2-(1,3-dimethyl-2,6-dioxo-1,2,3,6-tetrahydro-7H-purin-7-yl)-N-(4-isopropylphenyl)acetamide], (Fajardo et al 2008) Gentamicin, Amiloride, and Gadolinium. (Garcia-Anoveros and Nagata 2007) TRPM8 can be inhibited by 5-benzyloxytryptamine (5-BT), (Defalco et al 2010) N-(p-Amylcinnamoyl)anthranilic Acid (ACA), (Harteneck et al 2007) N-(3-aminopropyl)-2-((3-methylphenyl)methyl)oxy)-N-(2-thienylmethyl)benzamide hydrochloride salt (AMTB), (Lashinger et al 2008) ruthenium red, (Brignell et al 2008) BCTC, thio-BCTC, capsazepine, and protons. (Andersson et al 2004; Behrendt et al 2004)

3.1.2. Substances inhibiting cold signals

There are many substances that can inhibit TRPM8 and TRPA1 channels. (Cahusac 2009) The selection of a starting antagonist depends on their availability, delivery approach and toxicity. 5-benzyloxytryptamine and ruthenium red have very good water solubility and very low known half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values. The IC₅₀ of 5-benzyloxytryptamine (TRPM8 antagonist) and ruthenium red (TRPA1 antagonist) are 0.34 μM (Defalco et al 2010) and 3.4 μM, (Farris et al 2004; Garcia-Anoveros and Nagata 2007; Jordt et al 2004) respectively. If a 10 time the IC₅₀ concentration is to be reached in in vivo condition, doses of 1.03 mg/kg and 26.72 mg/kg for 5-benzyloxytryptamine and ruthenium red will be needed, respectively, assuming they are evenly distributed in body fluid. Similar dose of ruthenium red has been used in rats and proved effective for blocking capsaicin induced artery response, (Bari and Jancso 1994) but a dose range of 0.026-0.26 mg/kg is not effective in blocking cold-evoked activities in cutaneous primary afferents. (Dunham et al 2010)

3.1.3. Potential pitfalls and alternative strategies.

The TRPM8 blocker 5-benzyloxytryptamine (5-BT) is a tryptamine derivative that also activates the 5-HT_{1D}, 5-HT₂ and 5-HT₆ serotonin receptors. (Boess et al 1997; Buzzi et al 1991; Cohen et al 1992; Peroutka et al 1991) Ruthenium red is polycationic cell biology reagent that tightly binds to tubulin dimers and ryanodine receptor and inhibits intracellular calcium release. (Ma 1993) Ruthenium red is membrane-impermeant, (Bari and Jancso 1994) so it may not pass blood-brain barrier and block TRPA1 channels in central venous system. 5-BT is a most recently discovered TRPM8 channel blocker; its optimal doses for mice and rats are not clear. Infusion of RR at a dose of 10 μmol in rats weighing 300-420g for 10 min

prior to the infusion of 100 pmol capsaicin inhibited the vasodilatory response. The effects of these blockers are temporary, which is good for short-term treatment and recovery. The inhibition lasted for at least 15 min and the vasodilatory response was restored after 30 min. Considering the above mentioned factors, dose adjustment may be needed for achieving maximal efficacy and reducing potential side effects. Other antagonists that may serve as alternatives.

4. Inhibiting glycolysis and mitochondrial respiration chain

Observation showed that hibernators deliberately suppress their metabolic rate before entering hibernation, torpor or estivation (Wilz and Heldmaier 2000) which are followed by a decline of body temperature. During hibernation and torpors glucose consumption (Frerichs et al 1995) and mitochondrial respiration (Brown et al 2007; Staples and Brown 2008) are significantly suppressed. Therefore, it is reasonable to hypothesize that active metabolic suppression facilitates reaching targeted temperature and reduce thermoregulatory responses during therapeutic hypothermia for ischemic stroke. Glucose utilization can be inhibited by 2-DG; and mitochondrial respiration can be reversely inhibited by amobarbital. Decreasing energy demand by metabolic suppression is the classic method for achieving neuroprotection. Metabolic rate could be drastically reduced by hypothermia, (Astrup et al 1981; Berger et al 1998; Mori et al 1998) anesthetics and sedatives. (Astrup et al 1981; Warner et al 1996) Hypothermia seems to have its unique effect in delaying the time to terminal depolarization (Nakashima et al 1995) than metabolic suppression alone.

4.1. Using 2-deoxy-D-glucose as a glycolysis inhibitor.

2-Deoxy-D-glucose (2-DG) has been recognized as an antagonist of glucose metabolism for 60 years and its biological effects and working mechanisms have been widely studied. (Kurtoglu et al 2007) 2-DG is rapidly absorbed when being administered orally (T_{max} 0.5–1h) with a half-life of 5–10h. (Raez et al 2007) 2-DG has a similar structure to D-glucose, is taken up through the glucose transporters (GLUTs) and phosphorylated by hexokinase (HK) to form 2-DG-6-phosphate (2-DG-6-P), which is slowly utilized at a rate of less than 4% of its natural substrate, glucose-6-phosphate (G6P). 2-DG accumulates within the cell, competes with glucose for phosphoglucose isomerase (PGI), and noncompetitively inhibits HK. The LD₅₀ of 2-DG in mice by i.v. injection is 8000 mg/kg. (Vijayaraghavan et al 2006) It has been used in a range of 125-2000 mg/kg in in vivo studies for treating convulsion, (Gasior et al 2010) tumor (Boutrid et al

2008; Gupta et al 2005) and for inducing torpor.(Dark et al 1994)

4.2. Metabolic suppression.

About 87% of brain energy consumption reflects function-related activities,(Magistretti 2002) and could be suppressed to conserve energy. Slowing and isoelectric changes of electroencephalogram (EEG) occur during hibernation(Frerichs et al 1994; Walker et al 1977) and anesthesia.(Esmaili et al 2007) EEG burst suppression provides neuroprotection.(Doyle and Matta 1999) Barbiturates have been used for such burst suppression with proven efficacy.(Astrup et al 1981; Warner et al 1996)

4.3. Partial mitochondrial respiratory chain inhibition.

Inhibiting different sites on mitochondrial electron transporting chain will result in significantly different effect on free radical production. For examples, block of electron transport at complex I by rotenone reduces superoxide production on complex I,(Grivennikova and Vinogradov 2006) preserves electron transport chain and reduces cytochrome c loss during ischemia.(Lesnefsky et al 2004) Antimycin A (AMA) inhibits mitochondrial electron transport chain between cytochrome b and c.(You and Park 2010) This inhibition results in the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can be attenuated by rotenone.(Chen et al 2003) Different Complex I inhibitors also have different effect on ROS production. Rotenone, piericidin A and rolliniastatin increase ROS production whilst stigmatellin, mucidin, capsaicin and coenzyme Q2 prevent ROS production.(Fato et al 2009) Transient and partial mitochondrial inhibition reduces ROS production and protects ischemia/reperfusion related injuries.(Anderson et al 2006; Chen et al 2006; Stewart et al 2009) Rotenone is a widely studied potent irreversible inhibitor of complex I that can be used for modeling Parkinson disease, therefore not compliant with the purpose of neuroprotection in the proposed study.

4.4. Using amobarbital for metabolic suppression and partial mitochondrial respiratory chain inhibition.

Amobarbital is a short-acting barbiturate that (like all barbiturates) works by potentiating GABA-ergic effect and inhibiting glutamate receptors. Amobarbital weakly inhibits complex I at the same site that rotenone works. Inhibition of respiration through complex I by amobarbital is rapidly reversible.(Chen et al 2006) When being used at 2.5 mM in perfused rat heart, amobarbital inhibits complex I, reduces free radical production and protects heart mitochondria.(Chen et al 2006; Stewart et al 2009) For anesthesia amobarbital can be used at a dose of 80 mg/kg in rats.(Cohn et al 1976) Amobarbital is also the standard drug used in clinical for diagnosing

hemisphere functional preference in Wada test,(Baxendale 2009; Kim et al 2007) during which the mean aphasic time is around 1.5 minutes, and EEG slowing time is of 4 minutes.(Kim et al 2007) Mouse subcutaneous route LD50 for amobarbital is 212 mg/ kg. EC50 of amobarbital on the inhibitory postsynaptic currents (IPSCs) in neocortex is 0.103 mM.(Mathers et al 2007) Amobarbital is also a weak inhibitor for complex I with an IC50 of 1.2 mM.(Fato et al 2009)

4.5. Potential pitfalls and alternative strategies.

2-DG causes reversible decrease of phosphocreatine (PCr) and increase of ADP levels, and an irreversible reduction of the cytosolic adenine nucleotide pool.(Kupriyanov et al 1991) Intravenous administration of 2-DG (250-1000 mg/kg) in anaesthetised rats may cause hypotension. (Vijayaraghavan et al 2006) We may need to do dose adjustment for further reducing side effect and maximizing therapeutic potential. Other similar glucose analogs may also be considered as alternative choices. 2-fluoro-deoxy-D-glucose (2-FDG) is more closely similar to glucose structure and more potent in glycolytic inhibition, and also more cytotoxic than 2-DG.(Kurtoglu et al 2007) 3-methyl-glucose (3-MG) interferes with glucose uptake, but does not inhibit glycolysis.(Gasior et al) 3-MG has showed protective effects in hepatocytes cryopreservation.(Sugimachi et al 2006)

Amobarbital potentiates GABA-ergic effect, blocks AMPA-selective glutamate receptor, and inhibits mitochondrial complex I. Alternative method for metabolic suppression without inhibiting mitochondrial respiration can be considered. Pentobarbital may be one of these choices. Measurement of ADP to O₂ (ADP/O) ratio (Takaki et al 1997) or ATP/ADP ratio (Schwenke et al 1981) indicates that pentobarbital doesn't inhibit mitochondrial respiratory function.

4.6. Alternatives for mitochondrial inhibition.

Other potent complex I inhibitors that may also be considered for alternative choices, which include pyridaben, rotenone, piericidin A, and fenpyroximate(Schuler and Casida 2001). Complex I inhibitors can be grouped into three classes. A-type includes fenazaquin, fenpyroximate, fyrimidifen, piericidin A, rolliniastatin, 2-decyl-4-quinazolinyl amine, and AE F117233; B-type includes rotenone, epirotenone, amobarbital; and C-type includes capsaicin and 4-(p-tert-butylphenoxy)benzoic acid-3,4-dimethoxybenzylamide.(Okun et al 1999). Rotenone and piericidin A are 50,000-100,000 times more potent than amobarbital for inhibiting complex I.(Okun et al 1999; Schuler and Casida 2001). Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), inhibiting cytochrome c oxidase,(Collman et al 2009; Truong et al 2006) which is also reversibly inhibited during

hibernation,(Muleme et al 2006) can be considered as an alternative mitochondrial inhibitor. H₂S is able to make mice entering severe hypothermia or suspended animation at a low dosage of 80 ppm.(Blackstone et al 2005)

5. Preemptive suppression of thermogenic defense.

The phenomenon that hibernators enter into hibernation rapidly and recover from hibernation without causing injury is attributable to their suppressed, balanced, and tightly regulated thermogenesis. During entrance and in deep hibernation, plasma catecholamines (dopamine, norepinephrine and epinephrine) are significantly lower than cold-adapted levels. When a hibernator arouses from hibernation, catecholamines markedly increase.(Florant et al 1982) In addition, administration of norepinephrine and epinephrine may cause arousal from hibernation.(Lyman and O'Brien 1988) The hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis is least active during hibernation season, maintains a stable level during hibernation bouts and fluctuates in association with arousals.(Hudson and Wang 1979) Glucocorticoids are important for enduring and surviving hypothermia,(Musacchia 1988) and are closely balanced during hibernation.(Musacchia and Deavers 1978) During hibernation, significant decreases in thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) occurs in many regions of central nervous system including hypothalamus and preoptic area and fluctuates in different phase of hibernation.(Stanton et al 1982) Furthermore, administration of TRH during the entrance and maintenance phases of hibernation causes body temperature elevation(Tamura et al 2005). Central nervous system thyrotropin-releasing hormone is also reduced during estivation.(Kreider et al 1990) In dormant phase of hibernation total serum T3 (triiodo-L-thyronine) and T4 (L-thyroxine) are elevated but free T3 and T4 are decreased over active levels because of increased serum binding capacity and affinity.(Magnus and Henderson 1988; Tomasi et al 1998) Short term cold exposure activates the sympathoadrenal system (SAS), HPA axis, and hypothalamus-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis; it also increases cellular levels of TRH mRNA and CRH mRNA in neurons of the paraventricular nucleus (PVN). The neurally mediated central effect of cold can override the inhibitory effects of circulating hormones.(Leppaluoto et al 2005; Zoeller et al 1990)Theoretically, preemptive suppression of these systems will reduce thermoregulatory defenses and facilitate reaching target temperature during therapeutic hypometabothermia.

5.1. Major thermodefensing systems

The sympathoadrenal system (SAS), hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, and hypothalamus-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis are the major systems that mediate thermoregulatory responses, which are suppressed and tightly regulated during hibernation. We will preemptively suppress these systems by preadministration of reserpine, metyrapone, and iodine solution, which are all up-to-date clinical medications with proved efficacy but have not been used in therapeutic hypometabothermia yet. We will use the same methodologies and time frame for inducing acute middle cerebral artery occlusion, for delivering therapeutic hypometabothermia, for evaluating neurological function and infarction volume, for monitoring metabolic rate and core temperature, and for blood sampling and assays of electrolyte homeostasis, glucose, thyroid hormones, and catecholamine levels.

5.2. SAS suppression.

The SAS structural components have different preferences in responding to stimuli. The adrenal medulla responds very rapidly to single stress exposure; the sympathetic nervous system responds to HPA axis activation; adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) may directly stimulate sympathetic ganglia; the locus coeruleus-noradrenergic system that supplies norepinephrine throughout the central nervous system responds to repeated stress exposures.(Sabban 2007) The SAS system can be targeted at different levels by various methods for therapeutic purposes. Reserpine is well known to be a depletor for norepinephrine (NE), dopamine (DA) and 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT). Reserpine inhibits ATP/Mg²⁺ pump, which is responsible for sequestering neurotransmitters into storage vesicles located in the presynaptic neuron, resulting in reduction or depletion of catecholamines and serotonin from central and peripheral axon terminals in many organs, including the brain and adrenal medulla. It has been used as an antihypertensive and an antipsychotic as well as a research tool. This depletion in the adrenal medulla is slower and less complete than in other tissues. Reserpine LD₅₀ in rats is 420 mg/kg by oral route; 44 mg/kg by i.p. injection; 15 mg/kg by i.v. injection; its LD₅₀ in mice is 200 mg/kg by oral route; 52 mg/kg by subcutaneous injection. In experimental studies reserpine can be used in single i.p. injections at a dose range of 0.25-6 mg/kg for inducing gastric mucosal lesions in SD rats,(Ma et al 2010) and at 2.5 mg/kg i.p. 16 to 20 hr before experiments for its effect on nociceptive testing.(Nakazawa et al 1991).

5.3. HPA axis suppression.

The HPA axis functions through hypothalamic corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH), pituitary adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) and arginine

vasopressin (AVP), and adrenal glucocorticoids (GCs). HPA is a well-known stress response system, (Papadimitriou and Priftis 2009) having a close interaction with adrenomedulla. (Goldstein and Kopin 2008) The HPA axis can be targeted at different levels by various methods for therapeutic purposes. Metyrapone (Metopirone) reduces cortisol and corticosterone production by inhibiting the 11- β -hydroxylation reaction in the adrenal cortex, resulting in elevated ACTH level if pituitary gland functions normally. It is used as an HPA functional diagnostic test with urinary 17-OHCS measured as an index of pituitary ACTH responsiveness, and is also used for treatment of Cushing's syndrome. Metyrapone oral LD₅₀ in rats is 521 mg/kg. In clinical settings metyrapone is used at a dose of 30mg/kg at midnight per oral route and the plasma cortisol and 11-deoxycortisol are measured the next morning between 8:00 and 9:00 am. In many species, including amphibians, reptiles, rodents and birds, corticosterone is the main glucocorticoid hormone. It has been used in a dose range of 50-150 mg/kg in 0.5% carboxymethylcellulose at 30-min (Lowery et al 2010) to 4-h before experiments (Krugers et al 2000) for reducing corticosterone levels. In rats, metyrapone at dose of 150 mg/kg decreases locomotion. (Canini et al 2009)

5.4. HPT axis suppression.

The HPT axis functions through hypophysiotropic thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH), pituitary thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), and thyroid hormones T₃, T₄. The HPT axis is well-known to be stimulated by cold exposure. (Fuzesi et al 2009) The central nervous system norepinephrine (NE) potently stimulates the biosynthesis and proteolytic processing of proTRH. (Perello et al 2007) Induced hyperthyroidism is associated with activation of the HPA axis. (Johnson et al 2005) When being exposed to cold, TRH deficient mice cannot maintain their body temperatures. This is associated with hypothalamic TRH depletion and reduction in thyroid hormone. (Nillni et al 2002) The HPT axis can be targeted at different levels by various methods for therapeutic purposes. Iodine solution in pharmacologic doses produces rapid remission of symptoms by inhibiting the release of thyroid hormone into the circulation. It is used for emergency management of thyroid storm and for preoperative preparation of hyperthyroid patients for thyroidectomy. Many iodine solution formulae are available. The usual dosage in clinical settings is 2 to 3 drops (100 to 150 mg) of a saturated K iodide solution p.o. tid, or 0.5 to 1 g Na iodide in 1 L 0.9% saline solution given i.v. slowly q 12 h. In animal studies iodine solution can be added into drinking water by adding 1 to 5 drops of fresh Lugol's solution in 100ml, (Boatman and Moses 1951) or using 0.05% sodium. (McLachlan

et al 2005) Iodine solution can be used with a high dose safely (160 mg/kg in rats) by i.p. injection. (Sharp et al 1982) Mouse has a greater surface area/body weight ratio that is approximately 12-16 times of the ratio in human. When converted from human dose by this ratio, the dose will be 228-457 mg/kg/day for mice.

5.5. Potential pitfalls and alternative strategies

Reserpine is non-selective for monoamine neurotransmitters. It depletes NE, DA and 5-HT. Reserpine at high dose may cause gastric ulceration, hypotension, bradycardia, and drowsiness. For these reasons, selective degeneration of noradrenergic nerves can be considered as alternative approaches for suppressing the sympathoadrenal system. Pharmacological choices include N-(2-chloroethyl)-N-ethyl-2-bromobenzylamine (DSP-4, i.p.) (Jonsson et al 1981) or intrathecal (i.t.) 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA). (Nakazawa et al 1991) DSP-4 can pass through the blood-brain barrier and is effective at 50-100 mg/kg.

Alternative approaches for inhibiting HPA axis include siRNA for corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH) through intracerebralventricular delivery, the nonselective CRF receptor antagonist α -helical CRF, the selective CRF2R agonist Urocortin-3, the glucocorticoid receptor type I antagonist mifepristone (RU38486), the selective CRF1R antagonist, CP-154,526 (butyl-[2,5-dimethyl-7-(2,4,6-trimethylphenyl)-7H-pyrrolo [2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-yl]-ethylamine). (Lowery et al 2010)

Iodine solution is effective in suppressing the release of T₃ and T₄, but may also cause complications, which include inflammation of the salivary glands, conjunctivitis, and rash. Propylthiouracil and methimazole can be used as alternatives for suppressing HPT axis. Propylthiouracil in high doses also inhibits the peripheral conversion of T₄ to T₃. Another choice would be 3-Iodothyronamine (T1AM), which is a natural derivative of thyroid hormone. T1AM opposes the biological effects of T₃ and T₄, (Scanlan et al 2004; Scanlan 2009) induces profound hypothermia and bradycardia within minutes in mice, (Scanlan et al 2004) depresses metabolism via a rapid interruption of carbohydrate utilization followed by a compensatory rise in lipid utilization. (Braulke et al 2008) siRNA against prepro-TRH can be used through intracerebralventricular delivery for reducing TRH secretion. (Guissouma et al 2006; Landa et al 2007a; Landa et al 2007b)

The beta adrenergic receptor antagonist propranolol can be used as an alternative method for reducing the effects of epinephrine (adrenaline) and other stress hormones. Propranolol is also effective in inhibiting peripheral conversion of T₄ to T₃.

6. Conclusion remarks

To realize the thermogenically optimal and synergistic reduction of core temperature and metabolic rate, we propose novel strategies and practical approaches for therapeutic hypometabothermia: 1) blunting cold-sensing transient receptor potential (TRP) channels A1 and M8 so that to minimize the input signal that initiates thermogenic defenses; 2) delivering active metabolic suppression by amobarbital and 2-DG so that hypothermia will have reduced counteraction from metabolic process; 3) preemptively suppress sympathetic system (SAS), hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, and hypothalamus-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis by preadministration of reserpine, metyrapone, and iodine solution so that to defeat thermogenic outputs.

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Conflict of Interest

None

References

- Anderson TC, Li CQ, Shao ZH, Hoang T, Chan KC, Hamann KJ, Becker LB, Vanden Hoek TL (2006) Transient and partial mitochondrial inhibition for the treatment of postresuscitation injury: getting it just right. *Crit Care Med* 34:S474-82
- Andersson DA, Chase HW, Bevan S (2004) TRPM8 activation by menthol, icilin, and cold is differentially modulated by intracellular pH. *J Neurosci* 24:5364-9
- Andrews MT (2007) Advances in molecular biology of hibernation in mammals. *Bioessays* 29:431-40
- Astrup J, Sorensen PM, Sorensen HR (1981) Inhibition of cerebral oxygen and glucose consumption in the dog by hypothermia, pentobarbital, and lidocaine. *Anesthesiology* 55:263-8
- Bari F, Jancso G (1994) Ruthenium red antagonism of capsaicin-induced vascular changes in the rat nasal mucosa. *Eur Arch Otorhinolaryngol* 251:287-92
- Baxendale S (2009) The Wada test. *Curr Opin Neurol* 22:185-9
- Behrendt HJ, Germann T, Gillen C, Hatt H, Jostock R (2004) Characterization of the mouse cold-menthol receptor TRPM8 and vanilloid receptor type-1 VR1 using a fluorometric imaging plate reader (FLIPR) assay. *Br J Pharmacol* 141:737-45
- Berger R, Jensen A, Hossmann KA, Paschen W (1998) Effect of mild hypothermia during and after transient in vitro ischemia on metabolic disturbances in hippocampal slices at different stages of development. *Brain Res Dev Brain Res* 105:67-77

- Blackstone E, Morrison M, Roth MB (2005) H₂S induces a suspended animation-like state in mice. *Science* 308:518
- BMJ1900 (2000) Human hibernation. *BMJ* 320:1245
- Boatman JB, Moses C (1951) Radioiodine concentrations and clearances in rats receiving iodine, thyroid and propylthiouracil. *Endocrinology* 48:413-22
- Boess FG, Monsma FJ, Jr., Carolo C, Meyer V, Rudler A, Zwingelstein C, Sleight AJ (1997) Functional and radioligand binding characterization of rat 5-HT₆ receptors stably expressed in HEK293 cells. *Neuropharmacology* 36:713-20
- Boutrid H, Jockovich ME, Murray TG, Pina Y, Feuer WJ, Lampidis TJ, Cebulla CM (2008) Targeting hypoxia, a novel treatment for advanced retinoblastoma. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci* 49:2799-805
- Braulke LJ, Klingenspor M, DeBarber A, Tobias SC, Grandy DK, Scanlan TS, Heldmaier G (2008) 3-Iodothyronamine: a novel hormone controlling the balance between glucose and lipid utilisation. *J Comp Physiol B* 178:167-77
- Brignell JL, Chapman V, Kendall DA (2008) Comparison of icilin- and cold-evoked responses of spinal neurones, and their modulation of mechanical activity, in a model of neuropathic pain. *Brain Res* 1215:87-96
- Brown ET, Umino Y, Loi T, Solessio E, Barlow R (2005) Anesthesia can cause sustained hyperglycemia in C57/BL6J mice. *Vis Neurosci* 22:615-8
- Brown JC, Gerson AR, Staples JF (2007) Mitochondrial metabolism during daily torpor in the dwarf Siberian hamster: role of active regulated changes and passive thermal effects. *Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol* 293:R1833-45
- Buck CL, Barnes BM (2000) Effects of ambient temperature on metabolic rate, respiratory quotient, and torpor in an arctic hibernator. *Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol* 279:R255-62
- Buzzi MG, Moskowitz MA, Peroutka SJ, Byun B (1991) Further characterization of the putative 5-HT receptor which mediates blockade of neurogenic plasma extravasation in rat dura mater. *Br J Pharmacol* 103:1421-8
- Cahusac PM (2009) Effects of transient receptor potential (TRP) channel agonists and antagonists on slowly adapting type II mechanoreceptors in the rat sinus hair follicle. *J Peripher Nerv Syst* 14:300-9
- Cairns CJ, Thomas B, Fletcher S, Parr MJ, Finfer SR (2002) Life-threatening hyperkalaemia following therapeutic barbiturate coma. *Intensive Care Med* 28:1357-60
- Canini F, Brahimi S, Drouet JB, Michel V, Alonso A, Buguet A, Cespeglio R (2009) Metyrapone decreases locomotion acutely. *Neurosci Lett* 457:41-4
- Chen Q, Vazquez EJ, Moghaddas S, Hoppel CL, Lesnfsky EJ (2003) Production of reactive oxygen species by mitochondria: central role of complex III. *J Biol Chem* 278:36027-31

- Chen Q, Moghaddas S, Hoppel CL, Lesnefsky EJ (2006) Reversible blockade of electron transport during ischemia protects mitochondria and decreases myocardial injury following reperfusion. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther* 319:1405-12
- Cohen ML, Schenck K, Nelson D, Robertson DW (1992) Sumatriptan and 5-benzyloxytryptamine: contractility of two 5-HT_{1D} receptor ligands in canine saphenous veins. *Eur J Pharmacol* 211:43-6
- Cohn L, Cohn M, Taylor FH (1976) Measurements of brain amobarbital concentrations in rats anesthetized and overdosed by amobarbital and treated centrally with dibutyl cyclic AMP. *Life Sci* 18:261-5
- Collman JP, Ghosh S, Dey A, Decreau RA (2009) Using a functional enzyme model to understand the chemistry behind hydrogen sulfide induced hibernation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 106:22090-5
- Coupey SM (1997) Barbiturates. *Pediatr Rev* 18:260-4; quiz 5
- Dark J, Miller DR, Zucker I (1994) Reduced glucose availability induces torpor in Siberian hamsters. *Am J Physiol* 267:R496-501
- Defalco J, Steiger D, Dourado M, Emerling D, Duncton MA (2010) 5-Benzyloxytryptamine as an antagonist of TRPM8. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*
- Dhaka A, Murray AN, Mathur J, Earley TJ, Petrus MJ, Patapoutian A (2007) TRPM8 is required for cold sensation in mice. *Neuron* 54:371-8
- Doyle PW, Matta BF (1999) Burst suppression or isoelectric encephalogram for cerebral protection: evidence from metabolic suppression studies. *Br J Anaesth* 83:580-4
- Dunham JP, Leith JL, Lumb BM, Donaldson LF (2010) Transient receptor potential channel A1 and noxious cold responses in rat cutaneous nociceptors. *Neuroscience* 165:1412-9
- Esmaili V, Shamsollahi MB, Arefian NM, Assareh A (2007) Classifying depth of anesthesia using EEG features, a comparison. *Conf Proc IEEE Eng Med Biol Soc* 2007:4106-9
- Fajardo O, Meseguer V, Belmonte C, Viana F (2008) TRPA1 channels mediate cold temperature sensing in mammalian vagal sensory neurons: pharmacological and genetic evidence. *J Neurosci* 28:7863-75
- Farris HE, LeBlanc CL, Goswami J, Ricci AJ (2004) Probing the pore of the auditory hair cell mechanotransducer channel in turtle. *J Physiol* 558:769-92
- Fato R, Bergamini C, Bortolus M, Maniero AL, Leoni S, Ohnishi T, Lenaz G (2009) Differential effects of mitochondrial Complex I inhibitors on production of reactive oxygen species. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1787:384-92
- Florant GL, Weitzman ED, Jayant A, Côté LJ (1982) Plasma catecholamine levels during cold adaptation and hibernation in woodchucks (*Marmota monax*). *Journal of Thermal Biology* 7:143-6
- Frank SM, Higgins MS, Breslow MJ, Fleisher LA, Gorman RB, Sitzmann JV, Raff H, Beattie C (1995) The catecholamine, cortisol, and hemodynamic responses to mild perioperative hypothermia. A randomized clinical trial. *Anesthesiology* 82:83-93
- Frank SM, Higgins MS, Fleisher LA, Sitzmann JV, Raff H, Breslow MJ (1997) Adrenergic, respiratory, and cardiovascular effects of core cooling in humans. *Am J Physiol* 272:R557-62
- Frerichs KU, Kennedy C, Sokoloff L, Hallenbeck JM (1994) Local cerebral blood flow during hibernation, a model of natural tolerance to "cerebral ischemia". *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab* 14:193-205
- Frerichs KU, Dienel GA, Cruz NF, Sokoloff L, Hallenbeck JM (1995) Rates of glucose utilization in brain of active and hibernating ground squirrels. *Am J Physiol* 268:R445-53
- Fuzesi T, Wittmann G, Lechan RM, Liposits Z, Fekete C (2009) Noradrenergic innervation of hypophysiotropic thyrotropin-releasing hormone-synthesizing neurons in rats. *Brain Res* 1294:38-44
- Garcia-Anoveros J, Nagata K (2007) Trpa1. *Handb Exp Pharmacol*:347-62
- Gasior M, Yankura J, Hartman AL, French A, Rogawski MA (2010) Anticonvulsant and proconvulsant actions of 2-deoxy-D-glucose. *Epilepsia* 51:1385-94
- Goldstein DS, Kopin IJ (2008) Adrenomedullary, adrenocortical, and sympathoneural responses to stressors: a meta-analysis. *Endocr Regul* 42:111-9
- Greif R, Laciny S, Rajek A, Doufas AG, Sessler DI (2003) Blood pressure response to thermoregulatory vasoconstriction during isoflurane and desflurane anesthesia. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand* 47:847-52
- Grivennikova VG, Vinogradov AD (2006) Generation of superoxide by the mitochondrial Complex I. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1757:553-61
- Guissouma H, Froidevaux MS, Hassani Z, Demeneix BA (2006) In vivo siRNA delivery to the mouse hypothalamus confirms distinct roles of TR beta isoforms in regulating TRH transcription. *Neurosci Lett* 406:240-3
- Gupta S, Mathur R, Dwarakanath BS (2005) The glycolytic inhibitor 2-deoxy-D-glucose enhances the efficacy of etoposide in ehrlich ascites tumor-bearing mice. *Cancer Biol Ther* 4:87-94
- Hahn RG, Lofgren A (2000) Epinephrine, potassium and the electrocardiogram during regional anaesthesia. *Eur J Anaesthesiol* 17:132-7
- Harteneck C, Frenzel H, Kraft R (2007) N-(p-amylicinnamoyl)anthranilic acid (ACA): a phospholipase A(2) inhibitor and TRP channel blocker. *Cardiovasc Drug Rev* 25:61-75
- Heldmaier G, Ortman S, Elvert R (2004) Natural hypometabolism during hibernation and daily torpor in mammals. *Respir Physiol Neurobiol* 141:317-29

- Holzer M (2010) Targeted temperature management for comatose survivors of cardiac arrest. *N Engl J Med* 363:1256-64
- Hudson JW, Wang LC (1979) Hibernation: endocrinologic aspects. *Annu Rev Physiol* 41:287-303
- Johnson EO, Kamilaris TC, Calogero AE, Gold PW, Chrousos GP (2005) Experimentally-induced hyperthyroidism is associated with activation of the rat hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis. *Eur J Endocrinol* 153:177-85
- Jonsson G, Hallman H, Ponzio F, Ross S (1981) DSP4 (N-(2-chloroethyl)-N-ethyl-2-bromobenzylamine)--a useful denervation tool for central and peripheral noradrenaline neurons. *Eur J Pharmacol* 72:173-88
- Jordt SE, Bautista DM, Chuang HH, McKemy DD, Zygmunt PM, Hogestatt ED, Meng ID, Julius D (2004) Mustard oils and cannabinoids excite sensory nerve fibres through the TRP channel ANKTM1. *Nature* 427:260-5
- Jung JY, Lee C, Ro H, Kim HS, Joo KW, Kim Y, Ahn C, Han JS, Kim S, Oh KH (2009) Sequential occurrence of life-threatening hypokalemia and rebound hyperkalemia associated with barbiturate coma therapy. *Clin Nephrol* 71:333-7
- Karashima Y, Talavera K, Everaerts W, Janssens A, Kwan KY, Vennekens R, Nilius B, Voets T (2009) TRPA1 acts as a cold sensor in vitro and in vivo. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 106:1273-8
- Karpovich SA, Toien O, Buck CL, Barnes BM (2009) Energetics of arousal episodes in hibernating arctic ground squirrels. *J Comp Physiol B* 179:691-700
- Kim JH, Joo EY, Han SJ, Cho JW, Lee JH, Seo DW, Hong SB (2007) Can pentobarbital replace amobarbital in the Wada test? *Epilepsy Behav* 11:378-83
- Kimberger O, Ali SZ, Markstaller M, Zmoos S, Lauber R, Hunkeler C, Kurz A (2007) Meperidine and skin surface warming additively reduce the shivering threshold: a volunteer study. *Crit Care* 11:R29
- Kobayashi K, Fukuoka T, Obata K, Yamanaka H, Dai Y, Tokunaga A, Noguchi K (2005) Distinct expression of TRPM8, TRPA1, and TRPV1 mRNAs in rat primary afferent neurons with adelta/c-fibers and colocalization with trk receptors. *J Comp Neurol* 493:596-606
- Koerner IP, Brambrink AM (2006) Brain protection by anesthetic agents. *Curr Opin Anaesthesiol* 19:481-6
- Koht A, Cane R, Cerullo LJ (1983) Serum potassium levels during prolonged hypothermia. *Intensive Care Med* 9:275-7
- Kreider MS, Winokur A, Pack AI, Fishman AP (1990) Reduction of thyrotropin-releasing hormone concentrations in central nervous system of African lungfish during estivation. *Gen Comp Endocrinol* 77:435-41
- Krugers HJ, Maslam S, Korf J, Joels M, Holsboer F (2000) The corticosterone synthesis inhibitor metyrapone prevents hypoxia/ischemia-induced loss of synaptic function in the rat hippocampus. *Stroke* 31:1162-72
- Kubota Y, Toyoda Y, Kubota H, Asada A (1993) Epinephrine in local anesthetics does indeed produce hypokalemia and ECG changes. *Anesth Analg* 77:867-8
- Kupriyanov VV, Lakomkin VL, Korchazhkina OV, Steinschneider A, Kapelko VI, Saks VA (1991) Control of cardiac energy turnover by cytoplasmic phosphates: 31P-NMR study. *Am J Physiol* 261:45-53
- Kurtoglu M, Maher JC, Lampidis TJ (2007) Differential toxic mechanisms of 2-deoxy-D-glucose versus 2-fluorodeoxy-D-glucose in hypoxic and normoxic tumor cells. *Antioxid Redox Signal* 9:1383-90
- Kwan KY, Allchorne AJ, Vollrath MA, Christensen AP, Zhang DS, Woolf CJ, Corey DP (2006) TRPA1 contributes to cold, mechanical, and chemical nociception but is not essential for hair-cell transduction. *Neuron* 50:277-89
- Kwan KY, Corey DP (2009) Burning cold: involvement of TRPA1 in noxious cold sensation. *J Gen Physiol* 133:251-6
- Landa MS, Garcia SI, Schuman ML, Burgueno A, Alvarez AL, Saravia FE, Gemma C, Pirola CJ (2007a) Knocking down the diencephalic thyrotropin-releasing hormone precursor gene normalizes obesity-induced hypertension in the rat. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab* 292:E1388-94
- Landa MS, Schuman ML, Burgueno A, Alvarez AL, Garcia SI, Pirola CJ (2007b) SiRNA-mediated silencing of the diencephalic thyrotropin-releasing hormone precursor gene decreases the arterial blood pressure in the obese agouti mice. *Front Biosci* 12:3431-5
- Lashinger ES, Steinginga MS, Hieble JP, Leon LA, Gardner SD, Nagilla R, Davenport EA, Hoffman BE, Laping NJ, Su X (2008) AMTB, a TRPM8 channel blocker: evidence in rats for activity in overactive bladder and painful bladder syndrome. *Am J Physiol Renal Physiol* 295:F803-10
- Leppaluoto J, Paakkonen T, Korhonen I, Hassi J (2005) Pituitary and autonomic responses to cold exposures in man. *Acta Physiol Scand* 184:255-64
- Lesnefsky EJ, Chen Q, Moghaddas S, Hassan MO, Tandler B, Hoppel CL (2004) Blockade of electron transport during ischemia protects cardiac mitochondria. *J Biol Chem* 279:47961-7
- Lowery EG, Spanos M, Navarro M, Lyons AM, Hodge CW, Thiele TE (2010) CRF-1 antagonist and CRF-2 agonist decrease binge-like ethanol drinking in C57BL/6J mice independent of the HPA axis. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 35:1241-52
- Lyman CP, O'Brien RC (1988) A pharmacological study of hibernation in rodents. *Gen Pharmacol* 19:565-71
- Ma J (1993) Block by ruthenium red of the ryanodine-activated calcium release channel of skeletal muscle. *J Gen Physiol* 102:1031-56
- Ma XJ, Lu GC, Song SW, Liu W, Wen ZP, Zheng X, Lu QZ, Su DF (2010) The features of reserpine-induced gastric mucosal lesions. *Acta Pharmacol Sin* 31:938-43

- Magistretti P (2002) Brain Energy Metabolism. In: *Fundamental Neuroscience* (Squire L, Roberts J, Spitzer N, Zigmond M, McConnell M, Bloom F, eds), 2 ed.: Elsevier Science & Technology Books, 339-60
- Magnus TH, Henderson NE (1988) Thyroid hormone resistance in hibernating ground squirrels, *Spermophilus richardsoni*. I. Increased binding of triiodo-L-thyronine and L-thyroxine by serum proteins. *Gen Comp Endocrinol* 69:352-60
- Mathers DA, Wan X, Puil E (2007) Barbiturate activation and modulation of GABA(A) receptors in neocortex. *Neuropharmacology* 52:1160-8
- Matthew CB, Bastille AM, Gonzalez RR, Sils IV (2002) Heart rate variability and electrocardiogram waveform as predictors of morbidity during hypothermia and rewarming in rats. *Can J Physiol Pharmacol* 80:925-33
- McKemy DD, Neuhausser WM, Julius D (2002) Identification of a cold receptor reveals a general role for TRP channels in thermosensation. *Nature* 416:52-8
- McKemy DD (2005) How cold is it? TRPM8 and TRPA1 in the molecular logic of cold sensation. *Mol Pain* 1:16
- McLachlan SM, Braley-Mullen H, Chen CR, Aliesky H, Pichurin PN, Rapoport B (2005) Dissociation between iodide-induced thyroiditis and antibody-mediated hyperthyroidism in NOD.H-2h4 mice. *Endocrinology* 146:294-300
- Merchant RM, Abella BS, Peberdy MA, Soar J, Ong ME, Schmidt GA, Becker LB, Vanden Hoek TL (2006) Therapeutic hypothermia after cardiac arrest: unintentional overcooling is common using ice packs and conventional cooling blankets. *Crit Care Med* 34:S490-4
- Mirzoyev SA, McLeod CJ, Bunch TJ, Bell MR, White RD (2010) Hypokalemia during the cooling phase of therapeutic hypothermia and its impact on arrhythmogenesis. *Resuscitation*
- Mokhtarani M, Mahgoub AN, Morioka N, Doufas AG, Dae M, Shaughnessy TE, Bjorksten AR, Sessler DI (2001) Buspirone and meperidine synergistically reduce the shivering threshold. *Anesth Analg* 93:1233-9
- Mori K, Maeda M, Miyazaki M, Iwase H (1998) Effects of mild (33 degrees C) and moderate (29 degrees C) hypothermia on cerebral blood flow and metabolism, lactate, and extracellular glutamate in experimental head injury. *Neurol Res* 20:719-26
- Muleme HM, Walpole AC, Staples JF (2006) Mitochondrial metabolism in hibernation: metabolic suppression, temperature effects, and substrate preferences. *Physiol Biochem Zool* 79:474-83
- Musacchia XJ, Deavers DR (1978) Glucocorticoids and carbohydrate metabolism in hypothermic and hibernating hamsters. *Experientia Suppl* 32:247-58
- Musacchia XJ (1988) Endocrine regulation of carbohydrate metabolism in hypometabolic animals. *Can J Zool* 66:167-72
- Nahar N, Akhter N (2009) Effect of carvedilol on adrenaline-induced changes in serum electrolytes in rat. *Bangladesh Med Res Counc Bull* 35:105-9
- Nakashima K, Todd MM, Warner DS (1995) The relation between cerebral metabolic rate and ischemic depolarization. A comparison of the effects of hypothermia, pentobarbital, and isoflurane. *Anesthesiology* 82:1199-208
- Nakazawa T, Yamanishi Y, Kaneko T (1991) A comparative study of monoaminergic involvement in the antinociceptive action of E-2078, morphine and U-50,488E. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther* 257:748-53
- Neil MJ, Dale MC (2009) Hypokalaemia with severe rebound hyperkalaemia after therapeutic barbiturate coma. *Anesth Analg* 108:1867-8
- Nillni EA, Xie W, Mulcahy L, Sanchez VC, Wetsel WC (2002) Deficiencies in pro-thyrotropin-releasing hormone processing and abnormalities in thermoregulation in Cpefat/fat mice. *J Biol Chem* 277:48587-95
- Okun JG, Lummen P, Brandt U (1999) Three classes of inhibitors share a common binding domain in mitochondrial complex I (NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase). *J Biol Chem* 274:2625-30
- Papadimitriou A, Priftis KN (2009) Regulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis. *Neuroimmunomodulation* 16:265-71
- Peier AM, Moqrich A, Hergarden AC, Reeve AJ, Andersson DA, Story GM, Earley TJ, Dragoni I, McIntyre P, Bevan S, Patapoutian A (2002) A TRP channel that senses cold stimuli and menthol. *Cell* 108:705-15
- Perello M, Stuart RC, Vaslet CA, Nillni EA (2007) Cold exposure increases the biosynthesis and proteolytic processing of prothyrotropin-releasing hormone in the hypothalamic paraventricular nucleus via beta-adrenoreceptors. *Endocrinology* 148:4952-64
- Peroutka SJ, McCarthy BG, Guan XM (1991) 5-benzyloxytryptamine: a relatively selective 5-hydroxytryptamine 1D/1B agent. *Life Sci* 49:409-18
- Polderman KH, Peerdeman SM, Girbes AR (2001) Hypophosphatemia and hypomagnesemia induced by cooling in patients with severe head injury. *J Neurosurg* 94:697-705
- Raez LE, Langmuir V, Tolba K, Rocha-Lima CM, Papadopoulos K, Kroll S, Brawer M, Rosenblatt J, Ricart A, Lampidis T (2007) Responses to the combination of the glycolytic inhibitor 2-deoxy-glucose (2DG) and docetaxel (DC) in patients with lung and head and neck (H/N) carcinomas. *J Clin Oncol (Meeting Abstracts)* 25:14025-
- Reyes Toso CF, Linares LM, Rodriguez RR (1995) Blood sugar concentrations during ketamine or pentobarbitone anesthesia in rats with or without alpha and beta adrenergic blockade. *Medicina (B Aires)* 55:311-6
- Robson WL, Bayliss CE, Feldman R, Goldstein MB, Chen CB, Richardson RM, Stinebaugh BJ, Tam SC, Halperin

- ML (1981) Evaluation of the effect of pentobarbitone anaesthesia on the plasma potassium concentration in the rabbit and the dog. *Can Anaesth Soc J* 28:210-6
- Sabban EL (2007) Catecholamines in stress: molecular mechanisms of gene expression. *Endocr Regul* 41:61-73
- Sagalyn E, Band RA, Galeski DF, Abella BS (2009) Therapeutic hypothermia after cardiac arrest in clinical practice: review and compilation of recent experiences. *Crit Care Med* 37:S223-6
- Saha JK, Xia J, Grondin JM, Engle SK, Jakubowski JA (2005) Acute hyperglycemia induced by ketamine/xylazine anesthesia in rats: mechanisms and implications for preclinical models. *Exp Biol Med (Maywood)* 230:777-84
- Scanlan TS, Suchland KL, Hart ME, Chiellini G, Huang Y, Kruzich PJ, Frascarelli S, Crossley DA, Bunzow JR, Ronca-Testoni S, Lin ET, Hatton D, Zucchi R, Grandy DK (2004) 3-Iodothyronamine is an endogenous and rapid-acting derivative of thyroid hormone. *Nat Med* 10:638-42
- Scanlan TS (2009) Minireview: 3-Iodothyronamine (T1AM): a new player on the thyroid endocrine team? *Endocrinology* 150:1108-11
- Schalen W, Messeter K, Nordstrom CH (1992) Complications and side effects during thiopentone therapy in patients with severe head injuries. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand* 36:369-77
- Schuler F, Casida JE (2001) Functional coupling of PSST and ND1 subunits in NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase established by photoaffinity labeling. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1506:79-87
- Schwenke WD, Soboll S, Seitz HJ, Sies H (1981) Mitochondrial and cytosolic ATP/ADP ratios in rat liver in vivo. *Biochem J* 200:405-8
- Sessler DI (2001) Complications and treatment of mild hypothermia. *Anesthesiology* 95:531-43
- Sharp JG, Osborne JW, Cheng HF, Coop KL, Zimmerman GR (1982) Scintigraphy and distribution of labeled antibodies in rats with tumors. *Eur J Nucl Med* 7:28-34
- Sprung J, Cheng EY, Gamulin S, Kampine JP, Bosnjak ZJ (1991) Effects of acute hypothermia and beta-adrenergic receptor blockade on serum potassium concentration in rats. *Crit Care Med* 19:1545-51
- Stanton TL, Winokur A, Beckman AL (1982) Seasonal variation in thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) content of different brain regions and the pineal in the mammalian hibernator, *Citellus lateralis*. *Regul Pept* 3:135-44
- Staples JF, Brown JC (2008) Mitochondrial metabolism in hibernation and daily torpor: a review. *J Comp Physiol B* 178:811-27
- Stewart S, Lesnefsky EJ, Chen Q (2009) Reversible blockade of electron transport with amobarbital at the onset of reperfusion attenuates cardiac injury. *Transl Res* 153:224-31
- Story GM, Peier AM, Reeve AJ, Eid SR, Mosbacher J, Hricik TR, Earley TJ, Hergarden AC, Andersson DA, Hwang SW, McIntyre P, Jegla T, Bevan S, Patapoutian A (2003) ANKTM1, a TRP-like channel expressed in nociceptive neurons, is activated by cold temperatures. *Cell* 112:819-29
- Sugimachi K, Roach KL, Rhoads DB, Tompkins RG, Toner M (2006) Nonmetabolizable glucose compounds impart cryotolerance to primary rat hepatocytes. *Tissue Eng* 12:579-88
- Takaki M, Nakahara H, Kawatani Y, Utsumi K, Suga H (1997) No suppression of respiratory function of mitochondrial isolated from the hearts of anesthetized rats with high-dose pentobarbital sodium. *Jpn J Physiol* 47:87-92
- Tamura Y, Shintani M, Nakamura A, Monden M, Shiomi H (2005) Phase-specific central regulatory systems of hibernation in Syrian hamsters. *Brain Res* 1045:88-96
- Tomasi TE, Hellgren EC, Tucker TJ (1998) Thyroid hormone concentrations in black bears (*Ursus americanus*): hibernation and pregnancy effects. *Gen Comp Endocrinol* 109:192-9
- Truong DH, Eghbal MA, Hindmarsh W, Roth SH, O'Brien PJ (2006) Molecular mechanisms of hydrogen sulfide toxicity. *Drug Metab Rev* 38:733-44
- van Heerden PV, Chew G (1996) Severe hypokalaemia due to lignocaine toxicity. *Anaesth Intensive Care* 24:128-9
- Vijayaraghavan R, Kumar D, Dube SN, Singh R, Pandey KS, Bag BC, Kaushik MP, Sekhar K, Dwarakanath BS, Ravindranath T (2006) Acute toxicity and cardio-respiratory effects of 2-deoxy-D-glucose: a promising radio sensitizer. *Biomed Environ Sci* 19:96-103
- Walker JM, Glotzbach SF, Berger RJ, Heller HC (1977) Sleep and hibernation in ground squirrels (*Citellus* spp): electrophysiological observations. *Am J Physiol* 233:R213-21
- Warner DS, Takaoka S, Wu B, Ludwig PS, Pearlstein RD, Brinkhous AD, Dexter F (1996) Electroencephalographic burst suppression is not required to elicit maximal neuroprotection from pentobarbital in a rat model of focal cerebral ischemia. *Anesthesiology* 84:1475-84
- Wilz M, Heldmaier G (2000) Comparison of hibernation, estivation and daily torpor in the edible dormouse, *Glis glis*. *J Comp Physiol B* 170:511-21
- Wollenek G, Honarwar N, Golej J, Marx M (2002) Cold water submersion and cardiac arrest in treatment of severe hypothermia with cardiopulmonary bypass. *Resuscitation* 52:255-63
- Wood M, Shand DG, Wood AJ (1980) The sympathetic response to profound hypothermia and circulatory arrest in infants. *Can Anaesth Soc J* 27:125-31
- You BR, Park WH (2010) The effects of antimycin A on endothelial cells in cell death, reactive oxygen species and GSH levels. *Toxicol In Vitro* 24:1111-8

- Young JD, Taylor E (1998) Meditation as a Voluntary Hypometabolic State of Biological Estivation. *News Physiol Sci* 13:149-53
- Zhao S, Shao C, Goropashnaya AV, Stewart NC, Xu Y, Toien O, Barnes BM, Fedorov VB, Yan J (2010) Genomic analysis of expressed sequence tags in American black bear *Ursus americanus*. *BMC Genomics* 11:201
- Zoeller RT, Kabeer N, Albers HE (1990) Cold exposure elevates cellular levels of messenger ribonucleic acid encoding thyrotropin-releasing hormone in paraventricular nucleus despite elevated levels of thyroid hormones. *Endocrinology* 127:2955-62
- Zuurbier CJ, Keijzers PJ, Koeman A, Van Wezel HB, Hollmann MW (2008) Anesthesia's effects on plasma glucose and insulin and cardiac hexokinase at similar hemodynamics and without major surgical stress in fed rats. *Anesth Analg* 106:135-42, table of contents